

The Degree Of Applying Of Successful Transition Programs For People With Autism Spectrum Disorder To Work From Teachers' Perspective

Kawthar Abed Rabbo Muhammad Qawasma

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 21, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Autism Spectrum, Teacher, Family Participation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5799716</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify the degree of applying of transition programs for the successful work of with autism spectrum disorder, the study sample consisted of (152) male and female teachers with autism spectrum disorder from the age of (12-20) years, who were randomly chosen , and the results lead to an evaluation degree that contributes to the success of the transition of people with autism spectrum disorder to work represented in (The transitional evaluation - the individual transitional plan - family participation - cooperation with relevant external institutions - self-determination skills), where the degree of applying of successful transition programs on all dimensions of the study was large, and it was, respectively, in the dimension (transitional assessment, skill of self-determination, individual transitional plan), followed by (family participation, and cooperation with relevant external institutions) to a medium degree, with no differences in the degree of evaluation of successful transfer programs due to the variable (educational qualification, type of education program), and the researcher recommended the establishment of workshops to train special education teachers on the applying of successful transition programs to work in light of other variables according to students' needs.</i></p>

Introduction

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities recognized by United Nations General Assembly Resolution No. (611/61) on the right to equality of persons with disabilities with others, and to support the principle of equal opportunities by providing job opportunities that suit them, enhancing a sense of belonging to their community, and giving them a sense of respect and self-esteem (Al-Qahtani, Al-Quraini 2017) . Autism spectrum disorder is a developmental disorder that has a lifelong impact on the individual socially, communicatively, and behaviorally (Al-Jalamdah, 2016). In light of the continuous increase in their numbers, the need to take care of their future and involve them in the labor market increases ;To make them productive and independent individuals like the rest of society.

There is no doubt that the transition of people with autism spectrum disorder to work goes through many difficulties compared to other special groups, and the National Autism Society in the United Kingdom indicated (The National Autistic Society- NAS, 2018)That there are approximately (700,000) children with autism spectrum disorder Which is equivalent to the infection of more than one child for every (100) children, and the prevalence rate indicates (1 for 59) births, according to the statistics provided by the Center for Disease Control and Prevention in the United States of America(CDC, 2018) .Also launched (King Salman Center for Disorder Research ,2019) statistical surveys in the Kingdom is the latest locally and carried out by (the General Authority for Statistics 2017) where the number of people with autism spectrum disorder (53.309) person. Moving services are known as activities that Progress for students and their families; Todetermine their future after ending basic stage in education , and expected results ,with situation plan included earn them skills, and necessary experiences to achieve goals, in order to help in a their community participation Transition Services for Students with Disabilities , 2018).

The concept of transitioning to work for people with disabilities is a recent concept in the Kingdom .It requires reference to global practices, including a modelKohler, which is considered as one of the models directed to planning the transition that leads to successful outcomes after completing the school stage, such as moving to work, where the model identified five areas for planning for the transition, which are "individual-centered planning, student skills development, family participation, program structuring, and cooperation with external institutions with relationship" (Al-Maliki, 2020) .The evaluation process for the transition programs aims at making the appropriate decision for the training that supports the successful transition, according to his professional capabilities, and choosing the appropriate job for him (Al-Humaidhi and Al-Sartawi, 2018) .

Despite the legislation that prepares individuals with disabilities to work, between (50 to 60%) of people with autism spectrum disorder left school without educational or professional credentials in universities to engage in a specific job, and (76%) of them were unable to find work (Snell-Rood, Ruble, Kleinert, McGrew, Adams, Rodgers, 2020). On the other hand, a study confirmed Schipper et al., 2016 (that people with autism spectrum disorder possess many skills and abilities related to areas that require organization, accuracy and attention to detail, which helps in succeeding in a work environment that suits the nature of their differences.

Cheong & Yahya study was focused (2013) **On the effectiveness of the transitional plan in employing individuals with disabilities in Malaysia**, on a sample of (2) special education teachers, (4) employees with disabilities, (4) families of these individuals, (4) employers, and (5) coordinators of non-governmental organizations, and it was shown that the transitional needs of people with disabilities are not commensurate with the curricula in secondary schools, and the results focused on best practices for a smooth transition to work, represented in "transition assessment, and writing an effective transition plan from school to work focusing on vocational training. And not just academic, collaborative support from families and the community, and training in self-determination skills.

Al-Dosari (2016) pointed out the **factors for the successful transition of individuals with intellectual disabilities to work**. On a sample of (86) teachers, the results revealed the importance of (7) factors affecting the transition of people with intellectual disabilities to work. The "individual transition plan, vocational training factor for students, self-determination skills, cooperation with external institutions, social skills, family involvement, and academic skills" came in succession, with no differences due to gender and years of teaching experience.

Francis, Stride, Reed, Chiu pointed out (2017) **Family vocational participation in after-school education programs for people with intellectual disabilities from the teachers' perspective**. With the aim of identifying () obstacles to vocational family partnership, positive experiences of family participation, professional family partnership strategies), 23 employees from five universities in the American states participated in the study, and pointed out the importance of family participation, and its role in raising family expectations for its children, providing support and solving problems. to which they are exposed, which would improve the transitional results for them.

Sheppard, Timmons, & Zalewski study (2018) point out to **evaluate the effectiveness of a transition program to support the transition of people with autism spectrum disorder**. Sample of the study consisted of University of South Florida students aged (18-25) years, they applied a program called "The Learning Academy" to improve transition, use note and interviews with teachers, students, and parents things, and resulted in the acquisition of the students for skills self-awareness, self-respect and trust by self-independence, As confirmed on three domains to success the transitional program: "Knowing students on himself, his abilities, and training on skills of the work, the exercise of the acquired business skills, support and guidance from before family and teachers.

Al-Maliki's study (2020) deals with the **reality of the elements of transitional services and their inclusion in the individual educational program for people with intellectual disabilities from teacher's perspective**. On several elements of transitional services" self-determination skills, student and family participation and related external institutions, student vocational training", on a sample of (72) teachers. Because of the importance of these elements, with differences between their views according to the variables of gender, number of years of experience, and no differences according to the variables of educational qualification, and education program.

And in the past three decades, calls around the world need to involve people with disabilities in the community by providing them with employment opportunities have emerged, and take advantage of their abilities, At the local level, the Kingdom striving in its vision (2030) to enable people with disabilities and participate them into the labor market through the progress of rehabilitation programs and employment programs; Despite the lack of concern in the changeover process, and the lack of activation of transitional programs that preparation them for work; That is because of deprived planning that achieves important partnerships with related community institutions; It was necessary to pay attention to the transitional phase to preface for the world of work, and to progress the transition smoothly and easily. Based on the unsatisfied results of people with autism spectrum disorder in the work environment. In addition, the worries that families have about the work challenges of different nature and requirements, and the lack of concrete evidence that affects the success of the transition of people with autism spectrum disorder to work (Zureikat, 2016). The current study came to evaluate successful transition programs in a suitable way, for improving professional performance, and achieving social integration. According to the following questions:

1. What is the degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective?
2. Are there dissimilarities in the degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective as a result of the educational qualification variable?
3. Are there dissimilarities in the degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective due to the variable of the type of education program?

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The descriptive survey methodology was adopted ;to suit the purposes of the study, and depends on the description of the phenomenon as it is in reality.

2.2 Participants

The sample of study consists of all teachers with autism spectrum disorder, employees in public and private schools, and day care centers that their number is approximately (430) male and female teachers for the year 2021 AD, according to the statistics of the Department of Special Education. A simple random sample was selected consisting of) 152 (teachers, with (89) male teachers, and (63) female teachers .With the determination of the main variables (educational qualification, type of education program).

1- Educational qualification:

Table (1) Distribution of the sample members by educational qualification

Qualification	Frequencies	Percent
Diploma in Special Education	9	5.9%
Bachelor of Special Education	104	68.4%
Postgraduate studies in special education	39	25.7%
Total	152	100%

From Table No. (1) (9) sample of the study represent 5.9% of the total sample of the study with educational qualification (Diploma in Special Education), which is the lowest percentage, while (104) of them represent 68.4% of the total sample of The study has their educational qualification (Bachelor of Special Education), which is the highest percentage, and (39) of them represent 25.7% of the total sample of the study, and their educational qualification is (higher studies in special education).

Education Program Type:

Table (2) Distribution of the sample of the study by type of education program

Education Program Type	Frequencies	Percent
day care center	54	35.5%
State school	63	41.4%
Civil School	35	23.0%
Total	152	100%

From Table No. (2) (54) sample of the study represent 35.5% of the total study sample, the type of their education program in (day care center), while (63) of them represent 41.4% of the total sample of the study, the type of their education program in (public school), which is the largest percentage, and in the last place, it was found that (35) of them represent 23% of the total sample of the study, the type of their education program in (private school).

2.3 Instrument

After look overliteratures review such as (Al-Qahtani, Al-Quraini, 2017 ; Hedley, Cai, Uljarevic, Wilmot, Spoor, Richdale& Dissanayake 2018 ;(Snell-Rood, Ruble, Kleinert, McGrew, Adams, Rodgers, 2020 A questionnaire was prepared to collect data.

Five-point Likert scale was used for the responses of sample of the study, according to the following degrees of agreement: (very large - large - neutral - few - very few), and expressing the scale quantitatively, by giving each statement a degree, "very large (5) degrees, great (4) degrees, neutral (3) degrees, few (2) two degrees, very few (1) one degree.

For determining the length of each of the five Likert scale categories, the range was calculated by subtracting the upper bound from the lower bound ($5 - 1 = 4$), then divided by the largest value in the scale ($4 \div 5 = 0.80$), and then these were added the value to the lowest value in the scale ;(1) to determine the upper bound for this category.

The validity of the questionnaire was confirmed by presenting it to a number of mediators in the field of special education, to assess its quality, its ability to measure what it was prepared to measure, its relevance to the objectives, and the clearness of each statement and its relevance to its domains; to express an opinion in the event of any adjustment. The paragraphs that were collected (80%) or more were approved by the mediators, and they were taken out in the final form

In order to validate the validity of the internal consistency, a reconnaissance sample of (15) teachers was selected, by calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient .(Pearson's Correlation Coefficient) ;to know the degree to which each statement relates to the total score of the aspect to which it belongs.

Table (3) Pearson correlation coefficients for the questionnaire expressions with the total degree of the aspect to which they belong

The dimension	Item number	Dimension correlation coefficient	Item number	Dimension correlation coefficient
Dimension One: Transitional Evaluation	1	**0.598	4	**0.648
	2	**0.513	5	**0.581
	3	**0.505	6	**0.726
The second dimension: the individual transition plan	1	**0.768	7	**0.605
	2	**0.541	8	**0.850
	3	**0.875	9	**0.768
	4	**0.844	10	**0.872
	5	**0.716	11	**0.768
	6	**0.534	-	-
The third dimension: family involvement	1	**0.804	4	**0.770
	2	**0.538	5	**0.638
	3	**0.748	6	**0.901
Fourth Dimension: Cooperation with Relevant External Institutions	1	**0.767	3	**0.633
	2	**0.854	4	**0.687
The fifth dimension: the skill of self-determination	1	**0.753	4	**0.726
	2	**0.555	5	**0.852
	3	**0.587	-	-

From Table (3) the values of the correlation coefficient of each of the phrases with its dimension are positive, and statistically significant at the significance level (0.01) or less ;which indicates the truth of the internal consistency between the statements of the first domains, and their suitability to measure what they were prepared to measure .To check the **structural validity**, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated) Pearson's Correlation Coefficient) ;In order to identify the degree of correlation of each aspect of the questionnaire with the total score, the results were as follows:

Table (4) Pearson correlation coefficients for the fields of the resolution with the total score

The dimension	Total score correlation coefficient
Dimension one: assessment for transition planning	.779**
The second dimension: the individual transition plan	.889**
The third dimension: family involvement	.932**
Fourth Dimension: Cooperation with Relevant External Institutions	.916**
The fifth dimension: the skill of self-determination	.887**

From Table (4) the values of the correlation coefficient of each dimension with the total score are positive, and statistically significant at the significance level (0.01) or less ;which indicates the structural validity of the fields of the resolution, and their suitability to measure what they were prepared to measure .

The validity of the study instrument was confirmed using the validity coefficient Alpha Cronbach (Alpha Cronbach equation) Cronbach's Alpha (α),(Table No (5) .shows the values of the Alpha Cronbach stability coefficients for each of the axes of the resolution.

Table (5) Cronbach's alpha coefficient to measure the validity of the study tool

Questionnaire domain	The dimension	Number of items	Domain stability
The degree of application of successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective	Dimension one: assessment, transition planning	6	0.790
	The second dimension: the individual transition plan	11	0.929
	The third dimension: family involvement	6	0.875
	Fourth Dimension: Cooperation with Relevant External Institutions	4	0.838
	The fifth dimension: the skill of self-determination	5	0.801
General validity		32	0.954

From Table No. (5) The general validity coefficient of Cronbach's alpha is high, reaching (0.954), and it indicates that the resolution has a high degree of reliability that can be depend on in field applying, and that the stability coefficient is high for each domain.

A- Half-segmentation methodology:

The paragraphs of the questionnaire were divided into two parts (odd number paragraphs, and even number paragraphs), and the correlation coefficient between them was calculated, and the correlation coefficient was corrected by the Getman equation for unequal paragraphs according to the following law:

$$Guttman = 2 \left[\frac{S_1^2 + S_2^2}{S_T^2} \right]$$

whereas:

S_1^2 Variation in the degrees of the first half of the questionnaire

S_2^2 Variation in the degrees of the second half of the questionnaire

S_T^2 The overall variance of the test scores.

In the case of equal paragraphs, the Spearman-Brown equation = the modified correlation coefficient, according to the following equation: (Afanah and Nashwan, 2016).

$$R = \frac{2R}{1 + R}$$

Where R The correlation coefficient between the scores of odd and even items, and the results were obtained as in Table.(6)

Table (6) results of the split-half method to measure the validity of the questionnaire

The dimension	Number of items	Correlation coefficient before modification	Reliability coefficient
---------------	-----------------	---	-------------------------

Dimension one: assessment, transition planning	6	0.805	0.886
The second dimension: the individual transition plan	11	0.824	0.881
The third dimension: family involvement	6	0.848	0.918
Fourth Dimension: Cooperation with Relevant External Institutions	4	0.728	0.843
The fifth dimension: the skill of self-determination	5	0.562	0.739
general stability	32	0.815	0.883

From Table No. (6) The general stability coefficient is high, reaching (0.883), and this indicates that the questionnaire has a high degree of stability that can be relied upon in the field applying of the study.

3- Results

1-The first question :What is the degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective?

The mean scores for these dimensions was calculated to define the degree of applying successful transition programs .Table (7) shows the general results of this domain.

Table (7) responses of sample of the study to the applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective

NS	Resolution domains	Main score		Standard deviation	Ranking
		mean	degree of approval		
1	Evaluation Planning Relocation	4.7292	very significant	.373330	1
2	Individual transition plan	4.6130	very significant	.442220	3
3	family sharing	3.2423	neutral	0.3580	4
4	Cooperation with relevant external institutions	3.2039	neutral	0.40528	5
5	Self-determination skill	4.6803	very significant	.474100	2
	The degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective	4.0937	Significant	.39201	-

It is clear from the results that the degree of evaluation of sample of the study for the applying of successful transition programs to work was at mean (4.0937), that is, to a large extent according to the standard adopted in the study according to the Likert Five-Scale, it was found that the degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disability to work was represented in the dimension (evaluation Transitional) in the first place with an arithmetic mean (4,7292), to a very large degree, followed by the dimension (self-determination skill) with mean (4.6803), to a very large degree, followed by the dimension (individual transitional plan) with mean (4.6130), to a very large degree, and then the dimension (Family participation), with mean (3.2423), which is neutral, "medium", and finally, the dimension of (cooperation with relevant external institutions) came with mean (3.2039), with a neutral degree of "medium ."

The result is in contract with the study (Cheong & Yahya, 2013) which focused on effective practices in evaluating transition programs, including writing a transition plan to work, focusing on vocational training .Cooperative support by families and the community, and training in self-determination skills .Conducting several tests to define the current level of performance, individual needs and thus design the transition plan .Whereas, professional transitional assessment is the basis for successful planning ;As it is one of the main pillars for making decisions about setting transitional goals, to provide the student with the necessary skills in the work environment .The more it relates to his needs .This requires educating the family about its lofty role among team members, as a main source of information, for the success of planning, through its participation by attending meetings periodically to achieve the desired goals) .Shepard et al, 2018 ;(Francis et al., 2017.

The second question: Are there dissimilarities in the degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective as a result of the educational qualification variable?

The normal distribution test was performed Tests of Normality(Test Shapiro- Wilk)to examine the moderation of the data in the educational qualification variable in relation to the total score and the sub-axes, because most of the parametric tests require that the data distribution be normal, because the number of the sample in the categories was relatively small in the category "Diploma in Special Education" and the normal distribution can be exceeded for the rest of the categories because the size of the sample in the categories was relatively small. The sample among them is relatively large, and the distribution of data was not moderate in relation to the total score and for all axes in the category of Diploma in Special Education ;In order to find out whether there are statistically significant differences in the responses of the sample of the study according to the educational qualification variable, the non-teaching test Kruskal and Lass was used.Kruskal Wallis TestTo identify the differences in teachers' perspectives in implementing successful transition programs due to the educational qualification variable, and the results came as shown in Table No:(8) .

Table (8) Kruskal-Wallis test results) Kruskal -Wallis (for the differences between the responses according to the educational qualification variable

The dimension	groups	The number	Mean rank	chi-square value	Alpha-level	
Transitional evaluation	Diploma in Special Education	9	87.11	3.763	0.152	Not statistically significant
	Bachelor of Special Education	104	72.06			
	Postgraduate studies in special education	39	85.88			
Individual transition plan	Diploma in Special Education	9	84.17	.3270	0.849	Not statistically significant
	Bachelor of Special Education	104	76.34			
	Postgraduate studies in special education	39	75.15			
family sharing	Diploma in Special Education	9	83.11	0.327	0.863	Not statistically significant
	Bachelor of Special Education	104	75.53			
	Postgraduate studies in special education	39	77.55			
Cooperation with relevant external institutions	Diploma in Special Education	9	84.44	.7500	0.687	Not statistically significant
	Bachelor of Special Education	104	77.37			
	Postgraduate studies in special education	39	72.35			
Self-	Diploma in Special	9	80.72	.5770	0.749	Not

determination skill	Education			0.176	0.916	statistically significant
	Bachelor of Special Education	104	77.62			
	Postgraduate studies in special education	39	72.55			
Total marks	Diploma in Special Education	9	82.33	0.176	0.916	Not statistically significant
	Bachelor of Special Education	104	75.95			
	Postgraduate studies in special education	39	76.63			

The results of Table (8) show that the value of (Sig) for the total degree of the degree of applying the successful transition programs to work is equal (0.916), which is greater than the level of significance ;(0.05) which indicates that there are no differences at the level (0.05) in the teachers' views of the educational qualification variable .The result agrees with the study (Al-Dosari, 2016; Al-Maliki, 2020) that university education programs may be devoid of academic courses based on transitional programs for people with disabilities, and their importance in facilitating their successful transition to work.

The third question: Are there dissimilarities in the degree of applying successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective due to the variable of the type of education program?

The researcher used the parametric test "one-way analysis of variance" One Way ANOVA ;(to clarify the significance of the differences in the responses of sample of the study according to the difference in the type of education program variable, and the results were as follows:

Table :(9) Results of" One-way ANOVA) " One Way ANOVA (for the differences in responses according to the type of education program variable

The domain	Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean squares	F	Statistical significance	Comment
Transitional evaluation	Between groups	.551	2	.275	2.002	.139	Not statistically significant
	Within groups	20,494	149	.138			
	Total	21,045	151				
Individual transition plan	Between groups	.087	2	.044	.221	.802	Not statistically significant
	Within groups	29,441	149	.198			
	Total	29,529	151				
family sharing	Between groups	.329	2	.164	.619	.540	Not statistically significant
	Within groups	39,559	149	.265			
	Total	39,887	151				
Cooperation with relevant external institutions	Between groups	.489	2	.244	.778	.461	Not statistically significant
	Within groups	46,847	149	.314			
	Total	47,336	151				
Self-determination skill	Between groups	1.002	2	.501	2.267	.107	Not statistically significant
	Within groups	32,938	149	.221			
	Total	33,941	151				
The degree of application of	Between groups	.230	2	.115	.747	.476	Not statistically significant

successful transition programs for people with autism spectrum disorder to work from the teacher's perspective of their teachers	Within groups	22.974	149	.154			significant
	Total	23.204	151				

The results of Table (9) show that the value of(Sig)for the total degree of applying successful work transition programs equal to (0.476), which is greater than the level of significance ;(0.05) Which indicates that there are no differences at the level (0.05) between the sample responses with regard to the degree of applying successful transition programs due to the variable of the type of education program .The result agrees with the study (Al-Maliki, 2020) that there are no differences between the teachers' perspectives according to the education program, which indicates the teachers' conviction of the importance of evaluating a successful transition to work regardless of the educational environment.

Recommendations

- 1- Organizing workshops to train teachers on how to successfully transitional assessment of the student according to his needs and interests, and preparing and applying the transitional plan.
- 2- Directing decision-makers in education to establish partnerships with external institutions ;To ensure their participation in the transitional plan for the student, and to provide training and job opportunities for them, while activating the role of the family in the transitional program, and encouraging them to actively participate that would help their children in facilitating the transition after school.

References

- Jalameda, Fawzia Abdullah (2016). Measuring and diagnosing autism spectrum disorders in light of the diagnostic criteria contained in (DSM-4/DSM-5), Amman: Dar march.
- Al-Humaidhi, Basima, Al-Sartawi, Zidane (2018). Transitional services provided to students with learning difficulties in secondary school programs . Journal of Special Education and Rehabilitation, 6 (25), 1- 46, retrieved from <https://search.mandumah.com/Record/951341>
- Al-Dossary, Mubarak (2016). Factors for the successful transition of individuals with mild intellectual disabilities from school to work . Educational Sciences, 24(3),211-243, retrieved from <https://search.mandumah.com/Record/795731>
- Zureikat, Ibrahim. (2016). Vocational rehabilitation and transportation services for people with disabilities , Amman: Dar Al Masirah.
- Human Resources Development Fund. (2017). Job Accommodations for Persons with Autism Spectrum Disorder , Saudi Arabia.
- Afana, Ezzo, Nashwan, Tayseer (2016). Recent trends in educational measurement and evaluation . i 1. Gaza: Samir Mansour Library.
- Al-Qahtani, Basheer, Al-Quraini, Turkish (2017). The use of transitional plans in individual educational programs for female students with intellectual disabilities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Journal of Educational Sciences , 29(3), 409-433. retrieved from <https://search.mandumah.com/Record/842788>
- Al-Maliki, Hussein (2020). Elements of transitional services in the individual educational program for students with intellectual disabilities . The Saudi Journal of Special Education, (13) 115-140. retrieved from <https://search.mandumah.com/Record/1039741>
- King Salman Center for disability Research (2019). Statistics of people with disabilities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia . retrieved from <https://www.kscdr.org.sa/ar/stats>
- Cheong, L & Yahya, SH. (2013). Effective Transitional Plan from Secondary Education to Employment for Individuals with Learning Disabilities: A Case Study, Journal of Education and Learning (2), 1927-5250. DOI:10.5539/jel.v2n1p104
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC]. (2018). Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) | Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring (ADDM) Network , Retrieved 20 May 2019, from <https://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/autism/data.html> .

- deSchipper, E., Mahdi, S., de Vries, P., Granlund, M., Holtmann, M., Karande, S., Almodayfer, O., Shulman, C., Tonge, B., Wong, V. V., Zwaigenbaum, L., & Bölte, S. (2016). Functioning and disability in autism spectrum disorder: A worldwide survey of experts. *Autism research: official journal of the International Society for Autism Research*, 9(9), 959–969. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aur.1592>
- Francis, G. Stride, A. Reed, S. Chiu, CH. (2017). Family-Professional Partnerships in Postsecondary Education Programs: Perceptions of Professionals. *American Association on Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities*, 5 (4), 263-278. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1352/2326-6988-5.4.263>
- Hedley, D., Cai, R., Uljarevic, M., Wilmot, M., Spoor, JR, Richdale, A., & Dissanayake, C. (2018). Transition to work: Perspectives from the autism spectrum. *Autism*, 22(5), 528–541. doi: 10.1177/136236131668769.
- Shepard, J. Timmons, J. Zalewska, A. (2018). Research to Practice: Lessons Learned from the Learning Academy: Optimizing Transition Supports for Young Adults with Autism. *Research to Practice Series*, Institute for Community Inclusion, https://scholarworks.umb.edu/ici_researchtopractice/47.
- Virginia Department of Education. (2018). Transition Services for Students with Disabilities Retrieved from http://www.doe.virginia.gov/special_ed/transition_svcs/index.shtml
- Snell-Rood, C., Ruble, L., Kleinert, H., McGrew, JH, Adams, M., Rodgers, A., Yu, Y. (2020). Stakeholder perspectives on transition planning, implementation, and outcomes for students with autism spectrum disorder. *Autism*, 24 (5), 1164–1176. Doi: 10.1177/1362361319894827.

Author Information

Dr. Kawthar Abed Rabbo Muhammad Qawasma
Associate Professor of Special Education/ University
of Jeddah
